

A STUDY ON EFFECTIVENESS OF OPEN ERP WITH ACCOUNTING EMPLOYEES IN IT SECTOR WITH REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE

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Abstract:

ERP is an industry term for the broad set of activities supported by multi-module application software that help a manufacturer or other business manage the important parts of its business, including product planning, parts purchasing, maintaining inventories, interacting with suppliers, providing customer service, and tracking orders. ERP can also include application modules for the human resources aspects of a business. Typically, an ERP system uses or is integrated with a relational database system." The study is about implementation of open ERP in the system by removing the existing system in the company which is used in excel sheet and for that purpose a deep knowledge about open ERP was made and a survey was conducted with 27 employees of various companies and was analyzed by percentage analysis and chi-square as tools. The conclusion is that the open ERP has an efficient productivity based on time and cost which leads to reduction in employee ideality of the company.

Key Words: ERP, Human Resources & Application

Introduction to the Study:

A relational database management system (RDBMS) is a database management system (DBMS) that is based on the relational model as introduced by E. F. Codd, of IBM's San Jose Research Laboratory. Many popular databases currently in use are based on the relational database model.

RDBMSs have become a predominant choice for the storage of information in new databases used for financial records, manufacturing and logistical information, personnel data, and much more. Relational databases have often replaced legacy hierarchical databases and network databases because they are easier to understand and use. However, relational databases have been challenged by object databases, which were introduced in an attempt to address the object-relational impedance mismatch in relational database, and XML databases.

Statement of Problem:

Database management system plays a key role in storage and access of data in a company. But in some companies the employees may not be adopted for the implementation and growth of technology in the company due to lag of knowledge in the product.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To know about the concepts involved in database management system.
- ✓ To analyse the importance of DBMS along with the customers and the company.
- ✓ To know the relationship between the variables using tools.

Research Methodology:

Research Design:

The researcher propose is to first conduct a intensive secondary research to understand the full impact and implication of the industry, to review and critique the industry norms and reports, on which certain issues shall be selected, which the

researcher feel remain unanswered or liable to change, this shall be further taken up in the next stage of exploratory research.

Data Collection:

Primary Data:

Primary data is basically collected by getting questionnaire filled by the respondents. Data collection took place with the help of filling of questionnaires. The questionnaire method has come to the more widely used and economical means of data collection.

Secondary Data:

Information that already exists somewhere; having been collected for another purpose Sources include census reports, trade publications, and subscription services. Secondary source of data used consists of books and websites

Sample Size:

The researcher have targeted 80 people in the age group above 21 years for the purpose of the research. The target population influences the sample size. The target population represents the customer base of the company.

Tools Used:

- ✓ Percentage analysis
- ✓ Chi square analysis
- ✓ Anova

Review of Literature:

Z. Chen, (1991) Conceptual integration of existing information systems provides an alternative way of approaching a kind of metasystem, namely, meta-information systems. Since various external views can be generated from the same set of information systems for different information needs, a DBMS (database management systems) metaphor is a useful approach.

Roger M. Tagg, (1982) The different approaches to the term 'database' are distinguished by the differences between bibliographic and commercial databases. The two have resulted in different software development, namely IR and Database Management Systems (DBMS). The author explains the characteristics of DBMS, illustrated with 2 diagrams, for use with commercial systems. Factors in the design of commercial databases are discussed. Examples of software packages described are — ADABAS, BASIS, INQUIRE, LEXIBOSS. The author concludes that the division between IR and DBMS should narrow but that the microcomputer is not likely to provide the basis for such systems yet.

Analysis and Interpretation:

		Frequency	Percent
Gender of the Respondents	Male	16	59.3
	Female	11	40.7
	Total	27	100.0
Age of the Respondents	20-25	7	25.9
	26-30	8	29.6
	31-35	5	18.5
	36-40	2	7.4
	Above 41	5	18.5
	Total	27	100.0

		Frequency	Percent
Gender of the Respondents	Male	16	59.3
	Female	11	40.7
Educational Qualification of the Respondents	12th	4	14.8
	UG	10	37.0
	PG	12	44.4
	Others	1	3.7
	Total	27	100.0

Managing Information by the Organisation	Yes Totally	3	11.1
	Largely	5	18.5
	Partially	7	25.9
	To small extent	7	25.9
	No	5	18.5
	Total	27	100.0
Information on Assert Documentation by the Organisation	Yes Totally	8	29.6
	Largely	7	25.9
	Partially	6	22.2
	To small extent	3	11.1
	No	3	11.1

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the Gender of the respondents. Out of 27 respondents 59.3% are male and 40.7% are female which shows that most of the respondents are male in our study. 25.9% are 20-25 in age and 29.6% are 26-30 in age and 18.5% are 31-35 in age and 7.4% are 36-40 in age and 18.5% are Above 41 in age which shows that respondents who are 26-30 in age are more in our study. 14.8% are 12th in Education and 37.0% are Under graduates in education and 44.4% are post graduates in education and 3.7% are Other category in education which shows that respondents who are Post graduates in education are more in our study. 11.1% of the respondents are totally satisfied on the information managed by the organisation, 18.5% says the organisation meets its own expectation largely, 25.9% says that the organisation meets partially, 25.9 say it meets to small extent and 18.5% say that it meets to no extent which shows that most of the respondents said that the information was managed partially and to a small extent. 29.6% of the respondents are saying that they are totally satisfied on information on assert documentation, 18.5% says as largely, 25.9% says as partially, 25.9 say it meets to small extent and 18.5% say that it meets to no extent which shows that most of the respondents said that the information on assert documentation by the organisation is maintained totally.

Age of the Respondents * Demonstration of the Cost of Knowledge and Information Management:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between Age of the respondents and Demonstration of the cost of Knowledge and Information Management

H₁: There is a significant relationship between Age of the respondents and Demonstration of the cost of Knowledge and Information Management

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	51.792 ^a	16	.000
Likelihood Ratio	49.091	16	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	20.675	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	27		
a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .15.			

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the significant relation between Age of the respondents and Demonstration of the cost of Knowledge and Information Management which shows that the significance level is at 0.00 which is lesser than 0.005 were null hypothesis is accepted. And there is a significant relation between the demographic variable and the subordinate factor so while taking age in to consideration demonstration of the cost of Knowledge and Information Management can be taken in to consideration for the decision making process of the company.

Findings:

- ✓ Most of the respondents said that the information is created and captured are to no extent.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said that knowledge and information for its users for a large extent.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said that the conversations are adopted and captured partially.
- ✓ It shows that most of the respondents said that the conversations are adopted and captured partially.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents said that the information created by the organisation are destroyed when needed totally.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said the transferring record collections to another public body are partially strong.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said finding the key and critical information when it is needed are to small extent.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said accuracy and authentication of the corporate information are totally strong.
- ✓ Maximum of respondents are highly dissatisfied with the implementation of MIS open ERP in the organisation and satisfaction level on the new system.
- ✓ There is a significant relation between the demographic variable and the subordinate factor so while taking age in to consideration demonstration of the cost of Knowledge and Information Management can be taken in to consideration for the decision making process of the company.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Only minimum of the respondent said that they are satisfied on the information managed by the organisation which shows that the current database maintained in excel are not up to the mark and the employees are looking for new system to

be implemented in the company. So open Enterprise Resource Planning can be implemented in the company for satisfaction and security level of employees in the organisation.

- ✓ Majority of the respondents are saying that the cost and resource needs should be determined totally. So if new system is implemented in company both for employees and customers the cost and resource can be used in a effective way which leads to minimization of employee ideality in the company.
- ✓ There is a significant relation between the demographic variable and the subordinate factor so while taking age in to consideration demonstration of the cost of Knowledge and Information Management can be taken in to consideration for the decision making process of the company.

Conclusion:

ERP is an industry term for the broad set of activities supported by multi-module application software that help a manufacturer or other business manage the important parts of its business, including product planning, parts purchasing, maintaining inventories, interacting with suppliers, providing customer service, and tracking orders. ERP can also include application modules for the human resources aspects of a business. Typically, an ERP system uses or is integrated with a relational database system." The study is about implementation of open ERP in the system by removing the existing system in the company which is used in excel sheet and for that purpose a deep knowledge about open ERP was made and a survey was conducted and was analyzed by percentage analysis and chi-square as tools . The conclusion is that the open ERP has an efficient productivity based on time and cost which leads to reduction in employee ideality of the company.

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